

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Experimental Verification of Destructive Single-Event Effects in Silicon Carbide Power Devices (MANOEUVER)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA08-266
General application	<i>Silicon Carbide Power Devices for High Voltage, High Power Platforms in Space.</i>
Type of test	SEE, Heavy Ion
Group leader, Institute	Arthur Witulski, Vanderbilt University
Date(s) of the experiment	03/21/2024 (16 hours, 8 AM to 12 AM) and 03/24/2024 (16 hours, 8 AM to 12 AM)
Facility	RADEF
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	32

Objectives of the experiments

In this experiment, heavy-ion irradiation was performed with two variants of high voltage MOSFETs, as shown in Fig. 1 at the University of Jyväskylä Radiation Effects Facility (RADEF) with 2059 MeV xenon ions, with a linear energy transfer (LET) of 49.1 MeV/(mg/cm²) (i.e., the energy deposited per unit distance). The low epi-doping MOSFET variant has a breakdown voltage (BV_{DSS}) of 4500 V, whereas the high epi-doping MOSFET variant has a BV_{DSS} of 1800-2300 V. The structural difference between the devices is their different doping of the N- drift layer (the epitaxial layer). RADEF is one of just a few accelerator facilities in the world with enough energy and range to get ions all the way through the thick epitaxial layers of vertical power devices.

The goal of our test was twofold: First, to determine the effect of the differences in epi doping on the SELC (single-event leakage current) of the devices for ions at angular incidence. This test is of interest because ions in space are omni-directional, i.e., they strike the device from every direction. Second, we were interested in seeing if there was a difference in the amount of latent gate damage between the two epi doping variants. Latent gate damage due to ions is also a concern in space missions. There is very little ion irradiation data on high voltage SiC power devices available in the literature. We also brought calibration devices to compare our results at RADEF with previous work at TAMU (they agreed), and did a qualification test on some new models of SiC power devices for a research colleague.

Experiment test report

Fig. 1. MOSFET schematic cross-section showing the breakdown of the analysis of heavy-ion irradiation incidence angle (left) where the device under test (DUT) is rotated at 5° intervals from -30° to +30° along the pitch of the device (N+ substrate is not to scale). The equivalent schematic R-C model of the MOSFET is also shown (right), after [19]. The channel ($R_{channel}$), JFET (R_{JFET}), drift (R_{drift}) and substrate & drain contact (R_w) resistances are highlighted together with the gate resistance (R_G) and oxide capacitance (C_{ox}).

The SiC power MOSFETs and diodes were irradiated up to a drain-source bias of 200 V at different total fluences during each run at the RADEF accelerator. Both GE diodes and MOSFETs devices suffered latent gate oxide degradation when irradiated with Xe ions. Post-irradiation, the devices were stressed under a gate-source (V_{GS}) bias from -5 V up to 20 V, and the I_G - V_{GS} responses were recorded. Table 1 shows the device responses when a constant voltage bias was applied, and the heavy-ion fluence was increased by one order of magnitude in every subsequent irradiation run on the same device. The results suggest that the different epitaxial layer doping and the pre-strike electric fields across the gate oxide and within the device between the two variants plays a negligible role in their latent damage responses. As shown in Figs. 2 and 3, both devices suffer gate oxide breakdown (i.e., reaching current compliance) under similar test conditions. These figures are from our paper presented at the 2024 International Conference on Silicon Carbide and Related Materials (ICSCRM): “Analysis of Latent Gate Oxide Damage in Heavy-Ion Irradiated High-Voltage SiC Power MOSFETs,” by A. Sengupta¹⁾, C. Martinella²⁾, D. Ball¹⁾, K. Niskanen³⁾, P. Harris¹⁾, S. Kosier¹⁾, J. Hutson¹⁾, A. Sternberg¹⁾, R. Schimpf¹⁾, K. Galloway¹⁾, A. Javanainen^{1),3)}, U. Grossner²⁾ and A. Witulski¹⁾, where (1) is Vanderbilt University, (2) is ETH Zürich, Switzerland, and (3) is the University of Jyväskylä, Finland.

Note: We are testing high voltage SiC power devices. Many of these devices are experimental (made for research purposes), so they do not have part numbers in the usual sense of qualified parts.

Table 1: List of parts and intended test type.

<i>Device Type</i>	<i>Device Rating</i>	<i>Number of Devices</i>	<i>Test Type</i>	<i>Additional Tests</i>
<i>GE diodes</i>	<i>4500 V</i>	<i>19</i>	<i>Angle</i>	<i>Temperature</i>
<i>GE diodes</i>	<i>1500-2300 V</i>	<i>25</i>	<i>Angle</i>	<i>Temperature</i>
<i>GE MOSFETs</i>	<i>4500 V</i>	<i>14</i>	<i>Angle</i>	<i>Latent Gate Damage</i>
<i>GE MOSFETs</i>	<i>1500-2300 V</i>	<i>20</i>	<i>Angle</i>	<i>Latent Gate Damage</i>
<i>GE diodes</i>	<i>3300 V</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>Angle</i>	<i>N/A</i>
<i>GE MOSFETs</i>	<i>3300 V</i>	<i>6</i>	<i>Latent Gate Damage</i>	<i>N/A</i>
<i>Wolfspeed MOSFETs</i>	<i>600 V, 1200 V, 1700 V</i>	<i>10, 20, 10</i>	<i>Latent Gate Damage</i>	<i>Angle</i>
<i>Generic diodes</i>	<i>1200 V, 1700 V</i>	<i>10, 10</i>	<i>Baseline</i>	<i>Angle, Temperature</i>
<i>Generic MOSFETs</i>	<i>1700 V</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>Baseline</i>	<i>Latent Gate Damage</i>
<i>SSDI MOSFETs</i>	<i>900 V</i>	<i>10</i>	<i>Qualification</i>	<i>Angle, Latent Gate Damage</i>

Table 2: Runs to determine impact of ions on gate oxide of GE MOSFETs

<i>Device Bias (V)</i>	<i>Total Fluence (ions/cm²)</i>	<i>Expected # of ions striking the JFET region</i>	<i>Latent Gate Oxide Damage</i>	
			<i>Low epi-doping</i>	<i>High epi-doping</i>
<i>120</i>	<i>10²</i>	<i>0.75-1.5</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>150</i>			<i>No</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>200</i>			<i>No</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>120</i>	<i>10³</i>	<i>7.5-15</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>150</i>			<i>No</i>	<i>No</i>
<i>200</i>			<i>No</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>120</i>	<i>10⁴</i>	<i>75-150</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>150</i>			<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>
<i>200</i>			<i>Yes</i>	<i>Yes</i>

Fig. 2. I_G - V_{GS} plot of low epi-doping SiC MOSFET showing latent gate oxide damage post-irradiation, when irradiated with 2059 MeV Xe ions at 10^4 ions/cm² fluence and 150 V V_{DS}

Fig. 3. I_G - V_{GS} plot of high epi-doping SiC MOSFET showing latent gate oxide damage post-irradiation, when irradiated with 2059 MeV Xe ions at 10^4 ions/cm² fluence and 150 V V_{DS} bias.

The angle of incidence data was included in our paper “Effects of Incident Angle on Single-Event Leakage Current Degradation in Heavy-Ion Irradiated 4500 V and Hybrid SiC Power MOSFETs,” by A. Sengupta, C. Martinella, D. R. Ball, K. Niskanen, A. S. Senarath, S. Islam, P. M. Harris, J. M. Hutson, J. M. Osheroff, A. L. Sternberg, H. Kettunen, S. L. Kosier, U. Grossner, A. Javanainen, K. F. Galloway, R. D. Schimpf, and A. F. Witulski (same institutional affiliations as the first paper, plus J.M. Osheroff from NASA GSFC). This paper was presented at the RADECS Conference in Spain in 2024, and has been submitted to the IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science. A couple of the plots are shown below.

Fig. 4. SELC degradation as a function of tilting angle for MOSFET nominal variant irradiated with Xe ion in blocking condition at $V_{DS} = 525$ V. The maximum absolute values of drain (I_D) and gate (I_G) leakage currents are shown in red and blue respectively in (a). The variation of drain (ΔI_D) and gate (ΔI_G) leakage currents with respect to the pre-radiation conditions are shown in red and blue respectively in (b). The yellow regions correspond to SELC I ($\Delta I_D = \Delta I_G$) and the orange region corresponds to SELC II ($\Delta I_D \gg \Delta I_G$). The irradiation was started at incident angle of -30° and incremented in 5° steps until $+30^\circ$ incidence. The smoothed lines in the figure are added for eye-estimation only.

Fig. 5. Pre-radiation and post-radiation absolute values of gate current (I_G) shown versus gate-source voltage (V_{GS}). The drain-source voltage (V_{DS}) is kept at a constant 100 mV, while V_{GS} is swept from 0 to 5 V.

In general, it does seem like the gate current degradation is related to the angle of incidence, as can be seen in the two plots shown here. As the conclusion from our paper states: “Single-event leakage current (SELC) degradation is a concern for usability of SiC power devices in longer space missions

since it causes permanent increases in the device leakage current and acts as a cumulative effect in an already degraded device. Thus, mitigation techniques for SELC degradation are as important as for catastrophic failures such as SEB or single-event gate rupture (SEGR). Also, in MOSFETs, there are two different mechanisms for SELC: SELC I where drain-gate leakage occurs and SELC II where drain-source leakage occurs, and thus both needs to be studied analytically.

Experiments performed at TAMU Cyclotron reveals the behavior of the two different variants of MOSFETs. The SELC and SEB thresholds of the hybrid variant devices is observed to be similar to that of commercial 1200 V devices tested under similar bias conditions and fluences. The radiation hardness of the nominal variant devices is observed to show improvement over both 1200 V devices and 3300 V devices [15] tested under similar bias conditions and fluences.

Furthermore, the effects of incidence angle on the SELC response have been investigated for two different variants of SiC power MOSFETs. It is observed from the experimental results from RADEF that change in the angle of incidence of heavy-ions makes a significant difference in the device SELC response. Under constant bias and total fluence, a device is observed to have different behavior when the angle of incidence is varied. As seen from the experimental results, there is an angle of incidence threshold where for a given angle rotation off-normal incidence of the top of the device, SELC no longer occurs. For a higher LET ion at RADEF (Xe, 50.8 MeV-cm²/mg) and the device biased near the SELC threshold, the threshold was 15°(±5) off-normal incidence. Moreover, depending on the angle of incidence, the leakage path in the MOSFET is also observed to change, thus indicating that the angle of irradiation has an effect on the threshold for the different mechanisms of SELC, as previously reported as a direct consequence of drain voltage bias. .. Observation of the change in leakage path from changing the angle of incidence but keeping the drain bias constant is one of the key takeaways from this work. In space applications, the heavy-ions can hit a device from different directions and the results in this work show that the thresholds for SELC I and SELC II can vary with the angle of incidence similarly as varying the V_{DS} bias.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

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